

BIOQUEER IN: DIVERSITY OF THE SEXES

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Acknowledgments:

Hello! Welcome to this guidebook!

I'm Anne, a biologist and feminist, and I'm here to ask if you knew that biological sex isn't limited to just male and female? In fact, there is a diversity of variations that are part of human development.

Did you know that there is diversity in the gender expression?

In the world we live in, we accept Western concepts, but there is indeed a variety of gender that goes beyond male or female and man or woman.

Shall we build an organizational chart of the sexes?

"Male and female or man and woman" are terms we use to talk about how people are born, which we call biological sex. But deeply rooted in this concept is the idea of gender. This concept is binary and seems to be fixed. We also have other binary terms: masculine and feminine. We learn this in our family education and in schools, but are things really that simple?

Let's take a closer look and build an organizational chart on this subject, which is more complex today than we might think. Below is an organizational chart with society's binary view:

Biological sex and its diversity:

Biological sex and its diversity:

Sex differentiation occurs due to several genetic and hormonal factors starting in the eighth week of gestation. The production of testosterone and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) by the newly formed testicles results in the persistence of the Wolffian duct (which gives rise to the epididymis, vas deferens, and seminal vesicle) and the regression of the Müllerian duct. In fetuses with ovaries, there is regression of the Wolffian duct and persistence of the Müllerian duct (which gives rise to part of the vagina, uterus, and fallopian tubes). Testosterone production also promotes the formation of the external penoscrotal genitalia, while in its absence, the external vulvovaginal genitalia are formed.

Below, we have a diagram showing sex differentiation that occurs after sex determination!

ACHERMANN; HUGHES, 2025, p.905

From a biological point of view, there is what is known as sexual dimorphism, that is, two main categories: male and female. But that does not mean that all bodies fit perfectly into these two groups. There are natural variations that are part of human biological diversity. However, from an early age, we learn a simplified version of these concepts, often reduced to labels such as “masculine and feminine” or “man and woman.”

This way of teaching ignores both the complexity of biological sex and the existence of gender, which is not limited to biology. Later on, I will explain this difference between sex and gender in more detail and why it is so important!

Biological sex and its diversity:

Did you know that in contemporary scientific literature, biological sex is classified into five main dimensions: Chromosomal sex (genetic makeup, such as XX or XY); Gonadal sex (presence of ovaries or testicles); Phenotypic sex (external physical characteristics); Hormonal sex (sex hormone profile); Brain sex (neuroanatomical and functional differences). We will look at phenotypic sex below!

ACHERMANN; HUGHES, 2025, p.905

On the previous page, we looked at the formation and morphology of the internal genitalia of males and females. On this page, we will look at the morphology of the external vulvovaginal and penoscrotal genitalia (phenotypic sex). In both cases, we observe typical genitalia, that is, individuals without Differences in Sex Development (DSD). But what about individuals with DSD?

Biological sex and its diversity:

DSD arise during embryonic and fetal development. They can be caused by:

- numerical or structural variations in sex chromosomes,
- variations in genes involved in gonadal and/or genital development (leading to inactivation or activation),
- variations in the synthesis of gonadal and/or adrenal hormones.

Below is a summary of what we have seen previously and an introduction to DSD!

Level	Category / Condition	Description / Examples
Chromosomal Sex	Typical karyotypes	46,XX; 46,XY
	Chromosomal DSDs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 47,XXY (Klinefelter syndrome) • 45,X (Turner syndrome) • 45,X/46,XY (Mosaicism) • 46,XX/46,XY (Chimerism)
Gonadal Sex	Typical gonads	Testis; Ovary
	DSDs 46,XY and 46,XX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ovotestes • Hypoplastic gonad • Dysplastic gonad • Streak gonad
Phenotypic Sex	Male-typical phenotype	Penoscrotal anatomy (epididymis, vas deferens)
	Female-typical phenotype	Vulvovaginal anatomy (uterus, fallopian tubes)
	Atypical phenotype	Diverse forms of atypical genitalia

Development typical of the sex (endosex)

Sex Development Differences/Diversities (DSD)
Estimated prevalence of 1.7% of live births

AUTORAL, 2025

Did you see how complex biological sex is?

Let's introduce the importance of differentiating between body types: we have endosex and intersex. Endosex refers to a body with typical sexual development within the male-female binary logic. Intersex refers to the self-declared identity of people who have variations in sexual and reproductive anatomy and/or hormones, that is, people with DSD.

Not everyone with DSD identifies as intersex, but every intersex person is someone with DSD. Why does studying DSD help us understand the binary nature of sex and gender?

Gender and its diversity

Before we are born, do we already have a socially predefined gender?

Yes! In our society, a gender is imposed at birth that ends up correlating with biological sex.

The way we express our gender is influenced by what Western society imposes on us.

The new idea here is to understand that the way we view gender roles (what it means to “be a man” or “be a woman” in society) affects not only behavior, but also people's bodies—even changing biological aspects over time.

It is impossible to separate one from the other, and what we are always observing is the relationship between biological sex and gender: gender identity is also constructed within the limits of biology, just as biological sex is constructed beyond those limits. In other words, our beliefs about gender shape not only our behavior, but also the development and functioning of our bodies. That is why we need to study both, with a view to demystifying the subject and gaining a greater understanding of these variations.

Gender and its diversity

Gender construction

As already mentioned, even before we are born, we are assigned an intrinsic biological sex and gender. Often, these are related solely to our morphology!

Example: A boy is defined as such because he has male internal and external genitalia linked to sexual dimorphism (he may be a cis man—one who identifies with the gender assigned at birth).

Note that there is a binary understanding of what sex/gender is here.

Gender deconstruction

Gender deconstruction occurs when people do not identify with the gender assigned to them at birth or with their imposed gender expression. They generally identify as: trans women, transvestites, trans men, and non-binary trans people.

We can conclude that a set of biological factors has an intraspecific relationship with gender, thus both are unified into one thing in society.

Gender and its diversity

Gender deconstruction

Above, we discussed a little about the imposition of gender correlated with biological sex, but we forgot that there is a spectrum of diversity in human beings, both morphophysiologicaly and socially.

All that remains is to explain gender expression (how you express yourself socially) and sexual orientation (who you are attracted to). On the other hand, while both humans and animals have sex, only humans have gender. And now it seems that things have gotten quite complicated, right? And why should we biologists understand all this?

Implications and a new perspective

Studying anatomy and physiology today requires care so as not to exclude bodies that exist and are real. Even so, they are absent from our teaching materials, including textbooks. For this reason, the booklet was developed as a resource to help understand the diversity of biological sex and gender.

It is necessary to understand the diversity of biological sex and gender in order to have inclusive education in biology teaching.

We have reached the end of our guidebook, and now we will complete the construction of the organizational chart. It will be up to date if we include all the variations of sex and gender that we discussed above. We hope you enjoyed our booklet and that you have acquired up-to-date information on the subject!

Check out the organizational chart below.

Glossary

- **Androgen Insensitivity Syndrome:** A difference of sex development condition characterized by diminished or absent androgen signaling due to a genetic defect affecting the binding of testosterone or dihydrotestosterone to the androgen receptor.
- **Bipotential Gonads:** Undifferentiated gonads with the capacity to develop into either ovaries or testes.
- **Chordee:** A congenital condition affecting penile function and appearance, causing a curvature of the penis during erection.
- **Gender Identity:** A person's basic, subjective sense of themselves as male, female, or another gender identity (e.g., "intersex"). It develops over time and is not a direct function of genes or prenatal exposure to sex hormones.
- **Gender Role (Gender Expression):** The behaviors, attitudes, and personality traits that a society, in a given culture and historical period, designates as masculine or feminine, considered more "appropriate" or typical of the male or female social role.

Glossary

- **Gonadal Dysgenesis:** A difference of sex development condition characterized by the loss of primordial germ cells and atypical gonadal development during embryogenesis.
- **Granulosa Cells:** Somatic cells that surround the developing oocyte in the ovaries, protecting and nourishing the egg and playing a crucial role in hormonal regulation.
- **Klinefelter Syndrome:** A condition affecting only male individuals, occurring when an extra X chromosome is present (47,XXY).
- **Labioscrotal Folds:** Paired structures present during the undifferentiated stage of external genital development, responsible for forming the labia majora (female) and the scrotum (male).
- **Leydig Cells:** Steroid-producing cells in the testis.
- **Sertoli Cells:** support cell lineage in the testis essential to the primary organizers and nurturers of spermatogenesis.
- **Turner Syndrome:** A condition affecting only female individuals, occurring when one of the X chromosomes is missing or partially missing (45,X).
- **Virilization:** A condition in which female individuals develop androgen-induced characteristics, such as hirsutism (excessive facial hair growth).

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